

RADIOGRAPHIC MEASUREMENT OF VERTEBRAL HEART SCALE, SPHERICITY INDEX AND NUMBER OF INTERCOSTAL SPACES IN CATS WITH VARIOUS LUNGWORM INFECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Infection with respiratory nematodes in cats leads to functional disturbances in the activity of the cardiovascular system, finding expression in clinical and radiographic changes.

The purpose of this study is to determine absolute and relative heart size in cats infected by *Aelurostrongylus abstrusus* (Strongylida: Angiostrongylidae), *Troglostrongylus brevior* (Strongylida: Crenosomatidae) or mixed invasion by correlating heart size and selected skeletal structures.

Forty cats with confirmed pulmonary parasites infestation (22 with *A. abstrusus*, 6 with *T. brevior* and 7 with mixed invasion) are included in this study. Measurements were made on obtained lateral and ventrodorsal radiographs. The following cardiac indices are reported: vertebral heart score (VHS), the ratio between the length and the width of the heart and the number of intercostal spaces occupied by the heart silhouette.

Mean +/- SD vertebral heart score of all groups are between 7.14±0.22 and 8.1±0.89 vertebrae, SI is from 0.64±0.02 to 0.76±0.05. Heart shade occupy from 2.08±0.15 to 2.46±0.21 intercostal spaces. No significant statistical differences are found among the cats infected with lungworms and unaffected ones in control group, which leads to no signs of cardiomegaly in infected cats.

Key words: cats, pulmonary nematodes, radiology, cardiac indices.

Introduction

Thoracic radiography is part of diagnostics of patients with cardiac disorders. The radiographic diagnosis of such patients is based on change in the size and shape of cardiac silhouette and pulmonary blood vessels. Enlarged cardiac silhouette may serve as a reliable parameter of cardiac pathology (Guglielmini et al., 2014).

Feline pulmonary nematodiasis is most commonly caused by *Aelurostrongylus abstrusus* (Strongylida: Angiostrongylidae), colonizing bronchioles and alveoli, where *Troglostrongylus brevior* (Strongylida: Crenosomatidae) are localized in the trachea and the main bronchi. The severity of clinical manifestation depends on the extensity of invasion, co-morbidities, age, the general health and immune status of animals. The most frequently used method to diagnose aelurostrongylosis and troglostrongylosis is the isolation of L1s from faeces through Baermann technique (Elsheikha et al., 2016). The migration of these parasites in cats is associated with inflammatory changes. Their radiographic visualization depends on the time elapsed from infection (Travesa & Guglielmini, 2008), parasitic burden (Elsheikha et al., 2016) and often precedes clinical signs (Crisi et al., 2015; Genchi et al., 2014). The increase in pulmonary vascular resistance consequently to infection-induced vasoconstriction and vascular changes may lead to failure of the right ventricle to pump adequate

amount of blood through the lungs, increased diastolic pressure, which are clinically and radiologically manifested as right-sided congestive heart failure (Campbell., 2007).

The aim of this study is to evaluate the heart size in cats infected by lungworms through comparison of heart size with various skeletal structures, numerically expressed by cardiac indices VHS, SI and ICS, independent from examiner's subjective evaluation.

Materials and methods

Examined animals

From March 2015 to December 2021, a total of 339 domestic cats from 58 settlements in Bulgaria have been admitted to the Infectious and Parasitic Diseases Unit of the University Veterinary Hospital, Trakia University – Stara Zagora. At admission, owners have signed an informed consent with respect to the existing working protocol in the clinic.

To collect individual samples, not contaminated with soil, the cats were housed in individual cages with free access to food and water in line with welfare requirements (Ordinance 20 of 1 December 2012 of the Ministry of Agriculture and Food).

Methods of examination

Fecal samples were collected after spontaneous defecation in individual litter boxes. They were examined by the techniques of McMaster and Baermann for three consecutive days (Zajac & Conboy, 2012).

Based on results from parasitological examination, 41 cats were selected (22, 6, 7 and 6 infected by *A. abstrusus*, *T. brevior*, mixed invasions, non-infected controls, respectively).

Radiography

The selected cats were radiographed in lateral (L) and ventrodorsal (VD) projection using PHILIPS SUPER 50 CP-D stationary X-ray equipment (Hamburg, Germany) with exposure data 50 kV, 8.3 mAs. The digital processing of radiographs was done with iQ-CR ACE acquisition station DICOM-compatible iQ-VIEW/PRO version 2.7. software.

Radiographic measurements

The sphericity index (SI) was calculated by the formula:

$$SI = L/S$$

The vertebral heart scale (VHS) was determined by the formula:

$$VHS = (L+S) / \text{length of } T4\div T7.$$

The number of intercostal spaces occupied by the heart shadow was determined by the formula:

$$ICS = C5\div C7 / S$$

Where: L is the long heart axis, S is the short axis (perpendicular to L at the greatest heart width), C5÷C7 is the distance from the cranial margin of the fifth rib to the caudal margin of the seventh rib.

Measurements were performed on the basis of methods of Litster & Buchanan, 2000 (Fig. 1) In lateral thoracic radiographs, L of heart was measured from the ventral border of the largest stem bronchus, seen in cross section to the ventral contour of the cardiac apex. Thoracic vertebrae were measured beginning with the cranial edge of the fourth thoracic vertebrae (T4) to the caudal edge of the body of seventh thoracic vertebrae (T7). The S of heart was measured in the central third region

(from the cranial to caudal border of the widest portion of the heart), perpendicular to the L. C5÷C7 the distance was measured from the leading edge of rib 5 to the trailing edge of rib 7.

Table 1: Values (mean value ± standard deviations), 95% CI of cardiac indices SI, VHS and ICS in the cats included in the study

	SI	95% CI	VHS	95% CI	ICS	95% CI
<i>A. abstrusus</i>	0.66±0.08	0.62÷0.70	8.02±0.86	7.64÷8.40	2.17±0.28	2.08÷2.26
<i>T. brevior</i>	0.64±0.02	0.62÷0.66	7.14±0.22	6.91÷7.37	2.08±0.15	1.98÷2.18
Mixed invasion	0.76±0.05	0.71÷0.80	7.47±0.23	7.29÷7.66	2.13±0.18	1.96÷2.30
Controls	0.74±0.07	0.67÷0.81	7.07±0.9	6.13÷8.02	2.14±0.10	2.04÷2.25

SI – Sphericity index; 95% CI – Confidence interval; VHS – Vertebral heart scale; ICS – Number of intercostal spaces occupied by the heart shadow.

T – trachea; L – long heart axis from the carina of the trachea to the heart apex; S – perpendicular to L at the greatest heart width; T4 – fourth thoracic vertebra.

Figure 1: Graphical presentation of the main radiographic indices – ratio of the long (L) and short (S) axes of the heart and VHS (ratio of the sum of both axes and thoracic vertebrae size) and number of intercostal spaces occupied by heart size (Litster & Buchanan, 2000).

The heart size, vertebral length and C5÷C7 distance were determined in millimeters.

Statistical analysis

The mean values, standard deviations (SD) and 95% confidence intervals were determined for all parameters. The Student t-test was used to evaluate the statistical significance of differences (at $p < 0.05$) between control and infected groups.

Results

In the conducted clinical examinations cats infected with pulmonary nematodes showed a plethora of clinical findings characterized by shortness of breath, wheezing, mucopurulent nasal discharge, tachypnea and enlarged lymph nodes.

Most cats (i.e., 21/22) infected by *A. abstrusus* and all by *T. brevior* and mixed invasion, showed pathological patterns on thoracic radiograms. Thoracic radiographs revealed alveolar, bronchial, vascular, interstitial as well as mixed pulmonary patterns.

In lateral projection, the short heart axis was $2.08 \pm 0.15 \div 2.17 \pm 0.28$ intercostal spaces and was $0.64 \pm 0.02 \div 0.76 \pm 0.05$ of the long heart axis (Table 1). The inter-group differences in VHS, SI and

ICS, as well as between each of infected group versus the controls, were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). In all cats, VHS varied between 7.14 ± 0.22 – 8.02 ± 0.86 . The three studied cardiac indices did not undergo significant changes in the groups of cats. In animals with severe invasion as well as in aged animals included in the study, supposed to carry the infection from a long time, there was a trend towards increased VHS values.

Discussion

Radiologically detectable changes in the cardiac silhouette size are specific for pathologically altered heart structure (Litster & Buchanan, 2000; Guglielmini & Diana, 2015) and their extent could be used for assessment of disease severity (Farrow, 1994). Enlargement of the right ventricle of the heart was described by Vezzosi et al., 2020 and Dirven et al., 2012 in cats with aelurostrongylosis. A case of irreversible pulmonary hypertension and right-sided cardiomegaly was reported in *T. brevior* infection (Crisi et al., 2015). Enlarged cardiac silhouette was observed by Stepanović et al., 2020 on 2 out of 7 chest radiographs of cats infected by *E. aerophilus*.

This is the first study describing the diagnostic relevance of VHS, SI and ICS in cats infected with lungworms, although numerous studies reported the radiological findings in the course of natural and artificial diseases caused by these parasites (Traversa & Guglielmini, 2008; Genchi et al., 2014; Crisi et al., 2015; Lacava et al., 2017; Vezzosi et al., 2020; Napoli et al., 2023). The descriptions of the cardiac silhouette of cats in them assumed to be subjective, being based on observers' experience (although it is often ample), but not based on objective criteria such as the size of bone structures.

According to Sleeper and al., 2013, changes of VHS values within 8.0 and 9.3 suggested that the cause of feline dyspnea may be congestive heart failure as well as respiratory disease. VHS is very valuable for distinction of cats with moderate to severe left-sided heart failure from healthy animals (Guglielmini et al., 2014).

In the present study, the lack of changes in VHS, SI, ICS in cats infected with lungworms imply that the changes induced by parasites occurred slowly and the induced circulatory disturbances are insignificant.

Conclusion

There are no statistically significant differences in the studied cardiac indices (VHS, SI, ICS) among cats infected with pulmonary parasites, as well as between infected and non-infected cats. The results of the three methods show strong similarity. Cardiomegaly is not a consistent sign in cats infected by *A. abstrusus*, *T. brevior*. Its absence however does not exclude invasion with respiratory nematodes. Feline lungworm infections still are an underappreciated diseases and the reason for the lack of radiological changes in the cardiac silhouette, observed in the present study, should be investigated in the future.

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